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National Security and State Sovereignty: The Contemporary Nigeria Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This study specifically aimed at ascertaining the level at which the constituents of national security has impacted on the sovereign status of the Nigerian state in contemporary times. The background to this study holistically impressed that the ability of a state, through its machinery-the government to sustain its sovereign status cannot be exclusively be achieved through the instrument of coercion. The study in this context insinuated that the ability of a state to exhibit attributes of good governance through the satisfaction of the socio-economic needs of the citizenry was critical to gaining the loyalty and support of the people. The study revealed that in recent times, there have been a high rise in the level of economic and physical security in Nigeria. Hence, high rate of youth unemployment, high rate of poverty and hunger, kidnappings, killings, etc. have constituted enormous threat to national security in Nigeria. Consequently, the social stability of the Nigerian state has consistently been jeopardised. The study adopted the qualitative research design. It relied on secondary sources like textbooks, journals and materials from the internet to generate relevant data for the study. The study revealed that leadership failure, represented in poor management of the nation's economy, lack of respect for the rule of law and constitutionalism, abuse of public office privileges, abuse of the fundamental human right of citizens, public sector corruption, derogatory global image etc. constitute the factors that have over time, weakened the sovereignty of the Nigerian state and thus, impacting negatively on the country's national security status. Conclusively, the study acknowledged the unavoidable role of a politically independent state in restoring and sustaining the state's sovereignty and thereby improving its security status. The study therefore recommended that the current Nigeria's political leadership class at the centre should adopt an all-encompassing distributive economic policy and introduce reforms in public sector values and norms as salient remedies to the ever-plummeting sovereignty of the Nigerian state.

Keywords: Development, Economy, Government, Governance, Politics, Political Leadership

INTRODUCTION

The critical essence that prompted the creation of the state from a hitherto administratively unorganised society, has continued to remain a globally perceived imperative. Borrowing from the social contract theorists on state evolution, the societies that existed, prior to the formation of a formal institution called the state, were deemed structurally formless and anarchical in their social relations. Hence, it suffices to state here that the advent of the state was exclusively vital in the reformation and regulation of the crude and uncivilised behavioural tendencies that characterised the pre-state formation era. In corroboration with this position, Jimmy (2019), asserts that "the global significance of statehood as an alternative for a

rudderless societal structure, is justified by the role it plays in harmonising the human relation component” (p.48).

Therefore, the survival, existential status and permanence of the state are fundamentally embedded in the ability the government to ensure the guarantee of the security of lives and property of the human elements in the society. Of course, the security clause constitutes the principal pre-condition that engineered the quest for state formation. In line with this, Ayew (2017) re-echoed the inspiration of the social contract theorists which consists in the impression that the apprehensiveness of humans about the safety of their lives and property historically informed the underlying reason that necessitated the birth of a sovereign union (the state). Thus, the people willingly entered into such a contract of forming a sovereign state, with the strict understanding that, with the profundity of powers and authority lawfully bestowed on the state, the latter must be duty bound to exercise such powers judiciously with a view to maximally realising the object of the contract. As such, the relevance and sovereign capacity of the state depend on its ability to effectively perform such primary tasks.

However, the relevance of the sovereignty of the state cannot subsist only in the ability of the state to militaristically protect its citizens against physical harm. By extension, the protection of the citizens against economic hardship, economic exploitation, ecological disaster and environmental infirmities, all consist in the administrative abilities that promote the relevance of a state and secures its sovereignty. To buttress this claim, Edo & Ikelegbe (2014) observe that, “the pride of state sovereignty lies in the ability of the government to sustain the relevance of its mandate through the regular provision of socio-economic values to the citizenry” (p. 48). In agreement with this, Akinyetun (2020) posits that security challenges, defined in terms of physical attacks are originally fuelled by prevailing social and economic inordinances in a state.

Over time, the Nigerian state has been experiencing spates of decadence in the nation’s security structure. The surge in the level of youth unemployment, the alarmingly high rate of food inflation, low per capita income, high rate of hunger, etc. comprise some of the indices of economic insecurity currently bedevilling the Nigerian state. Expectedly, the above highlighted factors have the propensity to instigate social violence and civic unrest. According to Ilo et al (2019), “food insecurity is the worst form of insecurity; hence, it has the capacity to speedily degenerate into social disharmony and physical violence” (p. 5). In the opinion of Obiri (2018), “the vulnerability of young Nigerians to be enlisted in the membership of deadly terrorist and other crime-related organisations on several occasions, is buttressed by the steadily crumpling national economic reality- a trend that has left millions of physically vibrant youths jobless” (p. 98).

To this end, an understanding can be deduced from the views shared above by various authors, on the variants of security challenges as currently witnessed in Nigeria. Central to these arguments and opinions as adduced by these authors is the fact that National Security consists, not only in the existence of a barely minimised incidences of kinetic violence, disturbances or warfare, but also in the extent to which the economic wellbeing of the citizenry is guaranteed. In fact, the latter, as shown by the objectivity in the contributions of scholars as reviewed above, as well as with the prevalence of socially existential indicators on ground, has the capacity to have a significant effect on the former. Therefore, the core objective of this study is to critically examine the impact of national security in the sustenance of Nigeria’s sovereignty in current times.

Review of Concepts

National Security

As indicated in the introductory section of this study, the understanding of national security is not only limited to a condition of safety from physical harm against the citizenry, either internally or from across a country’s border. This is why Paleri (2008) defined national security as “a measurable state of the capability of a nation to overcome the multi-dimensional threats to the apparent well-being of its people and its survival as a nation state...” (p. 12). In a corroborative contribution, Jimmy (2019) describes the term, National Security as an all involving administrative capacity of a politically independent state to ensure the overall protection and defence of its citizenry. By implication, the adjectival description,

'overall', denotes an all-encompassing ability of the state to cater for the defence of its citizenry against physical violence or coercion, external threats or aggression, and economic hardship. Hence, such a constitutional obligation to protect these overall dimensions of national security interests is vested in the government.

A more comprehensive and intensively encompassing definition of the term, national security which is generally accepted and endorsed by the comity of nations at the international sphere, is that which recognises the imperativeness of an independent state to prioritise the fixing of the state's economy as a prerequisite for securing national security. In other words, national security from this standpoint recognises the relevance of the economic viability of a state vis-à-vis its relationship with the overall social stability of any sovereign state. Thus, social stability in this context, comprises the political, religious, civic and economic sectors of the state. Scholars who subscribe to this line of thought strongly hold the view that the economy is the core determinant of the nature of the social existence of any society. By implication therefore, national security according to these scholars is measured by the capacity of a society's economic status. Central to their argument is that the economy shapes the rest of the entire fabrics of a state's social existence. Hence, a resilient economy, defined in terms of maximum level of job availability, a satisfactorily good level of per-capita income and a generally affordable level of cost of living, can go a long way to minimize incidences of civic violence, crime and other aspects of security challenges in a state. Scholars like Adejumo (2019); Bekee (2021), stressed the impression that a relatively vibrant national economy has the potentials to translate to a relatively stable national security, symptomised by the existence of scarce incidences of social disturbances or crime. In their separate definition, Amogu (2018), posited that "it is unlikely that in any society where the majority of the citizenry are economically well-off, there will be rampant cases of upheavals and criminal indulgences" (p. 128). In corroboration to the above assertion, Agama (2020), rationalised that when the majority of the citizens of any sovereign state enjoy a maximum level of good governance, expressed in quality economic dividends, the same citizens would always reciprocate by being patriotic through the avoidance of tendencies to the disruption of national peace and security.

In fact, deriving from the perspective as conveyed above, National Security presupposes a social condition where the majority of the citizenry of a sovereign state willingly and patriotically comply with the lawful dictates that require a peaceful, harmonious and violent-free co-existence, without the instrument of coercion or force. Scholars who subscribe to this ideological base, are advocates for state's resort to the non-kinetic approach to securing and sustaining national security.

State Sovereignty

The term state sovereignty generally refers to the statutory capacity of a politically independent nation, state or society to exercise control over its subjects, without undue, indiscriminate or unsolicited external influence or encumbrances. It denotes the legitimate right of the state through a body of either elected or appointed functionaries generally referred to as the government to oversee the overall affairs of the state, independent of external control, supervision or undue influence. The concept of state sovereignty has its operational definition, anchored on dimensional approaches. The first approach presupposes that the leader or leadership of the state possesses or is vested with the supreme ability to wield their influence or power over their subjects without resistance, either within the precincts of the state jurisdiction or externally. On the other hand, the second approach entails the kind of supreme authority, power or influence of the leader or leadership of a state which is derived from a body of laws and legitimately conferred on the leadership by their subjects. The sovereign status of a state in this context must necessarily connote the two attributes of obligation and right. Sovereignty as an obligation refers to the performance of the statutory functions mandate on which the existence of the state is predicated. Fundamentally, the existence, as well as the relevance of the state is anchored on the delivery, through the lawfully established institution-the government, quality social services and benefits

The first approach to understanding the concept of state sovereignty emphasises the overriding influence and control by the leadership of a state over the citizenry without the input of the so-called citizenry to the model for governance in the society. By implication, the people who constitute the majority membership of the society or state are side-lined in the determination of what constitutes the body of rules, ethics,

etiquette and principles that govern the system of public governance in the society. Under this method, laws, processes and regulations are exclusively conceived and dictated by the ruler or ruling class and are henceforth, crudely enforced on the people. This approach to state sovereignty was the template created by the 17th century philosopher Thomas Hobbes in his 1651 social contract theory postulation. While propounding his social contract theory, Hobbes conceived of a society where a ruler exerts the most supreme, absolute, preponderant, overriding and in most situations, tyrannical influence over their subjects. Using this model, the ruler instrumentalises force and coercion to earn the loyalty and cooperation of their subjects, even at the expense of the latter. Central to this approach is that the ruler exercises the totality of administrative control of the affairs of the state or society however inordinate and underserving, with zero tolerance for protest and rebellion from their subjects. This approach is classified under absolute sovereignty and is usually adopted by military and monarchical systems of government.

In politically independent states where democracy is practised, sovereignty is invariably a reflection of the will and mandate of the people. Hence, from a democratic perspective, state sovereignty can be defined as the ability of a sovereign state, through its machinery-the government to independently administer and coordinate the overall affairs of the state, including the loyalty of the citizenry, as guided by the constitution. The definition above is in agreement with the definition provided by Nweke and Nwoko (2021) who defined state sovereignty as “a constitutionally privileged capacity of the ruling class of any politically independent nation-state to wield the supreme authority to enforce loyalty and control over its territory. Also, it connotes the ability of such a nation-state to conduct independently, its foreign affairs without undue external influence and encumbrances,” (p. 262). However, according to Nweke and Nwoko (2021), such a constitutional privilege must be conditioned on the delivery of quality governance. State sovereignty also denotes the legitimately deserving capacity or right of any politically independent nation to conduct its foreign relations independently without external influence or involvement in the determination of the principles and strategies of such processes. State sovereignty in this context simply involves the ability of a politically independent state to conceive and implement foreign policies, favourable, suitable and convenient to its local interest. The ability of a sovereign state to independently conduct its foreign relations through the enactment of foreign policies involves a comprehensive and far-reaching effort in covering the various areas of foreign policy initiation. These areas include, diplomacy, trade and economic relations, security, infrastructural development and sundry international collaborations on inter-regional development. The core objective of the various independent states within the ambit of the comity of nations while setting its foreign policies is to promote their respective national interests.

A Critical Overview of the Nature of State Sovereignty in Contemporary Nigerian Situation.

Speaking from a general perspective, state sovereignty denotes the capacity of the leadership of any politically independent state to manage its affairs both locally and internationally. The management of its local and international affairs in this context includes the ability of an independent state’s leadership to enforce laws, regulations and discipline within its jurisdiction with the majority support and cooperation of the citizenry, and with minimal incidences of internal resistance and civic disturbances. The existing social scenario would thus, be projected at the international scene. Nigeria, being a country that has sustained an uninterrupted era of democratic dispensation since 1999 cannot boast of convincingly exhibiting the standards and factors that qualify a politically independent country to sustain its internal sovereign status. Hence, the attainment of a sovereign status for any politically independent state is expected to possess the following qualities:

- i. The ability of such a politically independent state to be economically independent in all aspects. This is further determined by the ability of such state to have an appreciably high degree of gainfully employed citizens, sustainable income, a very minimal level of hunger, strong agricultural base and the pre-eminence export over import.
- ii. Strict adherence to the rule of law and due process in the act of public governance.
- iii. Respect for and preservation of the fundamental human rights of citizens
- iv. Transparent and credible electoral process.

- v. The maximum level of guarantee in the security of lives and property of citizens
- vi. Territorial border integrity
- vii. Good governance

Unfortunately, the Nigerian situation represents an exact contradiction to the impression conveyed above. In current times, Nigeria's wobbling economic posture has been reflecting in the social environment, with evident signs of multi-faceted instabilities. The sustained trends of poor economic performances in Nigeria over time, has continued to ensure a steady rise in the level of poverty, social despondency, desperation, destitution, increased cases of mental health, incessant spike in cases of criminality and sundry manifestations of unhealthy social existence. Such prevailing social situation, when paired side by side with what state sovereignty stands for, both in content and in context, ranks Nigeria very low with regards to the attainment of a sovereign status as a politically independent nation. Consequently, this experience has called to question, the status of Nigeria as a sovereign nation. According to Kolawole (2021), the claim to the attainment of sovereignty by politically independent nations can be ascertained by the evidence of good governance in the multi-sectoral existence of nations. Hence, the economy, politics, social environment, security and the nation's global image constitute the areas where good governance is measured. The various sectors also constitute the basis on which the sovereignty of any politically independent country is judged.

The Economy

The economy of any nation constitutes the backbone that determines the physical survival and existence of such a nation. In several sectors of the Nigerian economy like labour, health, industry, human capital development, agriculture, there exists, reliable data to prove that the country's economic base has been surviving on a fragile threshold. A study carried out by Oye, Ibrahim & Ahmad (2011), informed that from the years, 2000 to 2008, a surge in the degree of unemployment gave rise to an attendant decrease in the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). To give assent to the claim that the unemployment rate in Nigeria maintains a steady increase, in the year 2017, the National Bureau of Statistics reported that Nigeria's unemployment rate was at 18.8 percent in the third quarter of that year. But, by the third quarter of 2018, the figure, according to the NBS had climbed to 23.1 percent. The National Bureau of Statistics also revealed that the figure of underemployment rate as at 2018 was 20.1. This situation, according to reports from the NBS has been having a corresponding consequence in the rise in national poverty level. Hence, according to NBS report, the rate of poverty in Nigeria has surged from 40.1% in 2018 to 47% in 2024.

As a politically independent country which boasts of being a sovereign nation, the Nigerian state unfortunately does not have a strong agricultural base, viable enough to achieve food security for its citizens. Instead, over the years, the country has been depending on food importation to cater for its ever-growing population. This has in turn, escalated incidences of food insecurity and hunger. Hence, it is on record that the number of food insecure Nigerians significantly increased from 66.2 million in the first quarter of 2023 to 100 million in the first quarter of 2024. Also, data from the World Food Programme (WFP) shows that 43.7 million Nigerians in the second quarter of 2024 are living in acute hunger (Tunji, 2024).

In the aspect of healthcare delivery, Nigeria's healthcare system has over the years, experienced a worrisome form of deterioration. According to a study conducted by Emodi (2024), most public medical outfits in Nigeria are poorly equipped. Emodi (2024) further informed that, especially at the level of primary healthcare delivery system, in over 80% of surveyed clinics around the federation, there was evident lack of modern and advanced medical facilities. Also, the study reported cases of overcrowding of patients due to lack of adequate provision of bed spaces and manpower, lack of drugs and medical diagnosis instruments. The root cause of the deteriorating level of healthcare system can allegedly be attributed to the fact that the leadership of the Nigerian state, over the years has failed to conform to international best practices in the health sector. For instance, in the aftermath of the Abuja Declaration of 2001 which mandated African Heads of State under the umbrella of African Union to commit 15% of its annual budget to the health sector, the best that the Nigerian state has done with regards to budgetary allocation to the health sector was in 2012 when the country allocated up to 6.08% of her national budget

to the health sector. Since 2012, Nigeria has been experiencing a downward slide in her budgetary allocation to the health sector. In fact, in the 2024 budget, only a paltry 4.06% budgetary allocation was made for the health sector (Fasan, 2024).

Politics

Over the years, especially since the inception of the fourth republic, Nigeria's political environment has been characterised by the most reckless display of constitutional breaches, undermining of the rule of law and due process, flagrant abuses of the fundamental human right of citizens and the deliberate disregard to the workings of the principle of separation of powers as well as checks and balances among the three organs of government. Also, there is a high level of official impunity in the nation's bureaucratic structure-a tendency which over the years, has continued to be shielded by the thriving of political/bureaucratic corruption in the nation's public service system. Again, poor system of accountability in governance by public office holders in Nigeria also highlights the extent to which Nigeria's political system cannot defend the sovereignty of the Nigerian state. The poor accountability syndrome in our public institutions in Nigeria has often taken the form of high cost of governance, leading to financial recklessness by political office holders. Empirical evidences of several cases of abuse of public office by politicians and other categories of public office holders abound. The decision by the presidency in 2023 to spend N21 billion for the renovation of the Vice President's residence amidst high level of widespread poverty and hunger was a demonstration of high level of insensitivity and irresponsibility. Also, the declaration by the Nigerian President, Bola Ahmed Tinubu of a State of Emergency in Rivers State as well as the concomitant suspension of a duly elected governor of the state and the members of the State House Assembly, has been described by critics, both in Nigeria and the international community as a brazen display of unconstitutionality (Majeed, 2024; Mustapha, 2025).

Security

Among the fundamental functions of government in any politically independent state is the protection of the lives and property of its citizens. Thus, the provision of adequate security for the citizenry underscores the most vital essence for state's existence. For over a decade now, the most bedevilling form of security challenges have confronted the Nigerian public space and have continued to trend almost on daily basis, on both national and international news outlets. The boko haram and ISWAP terrorist sects in the north east, Fulani herdsmen onslaught in the north west and northcentral, kidnapping for ransom and random killings in the south east and south-south regions, as well as other forms of security challenges across many parts of the country in recent times, have confined to threaten the peace and social stability of the Nigerian state. In most cases, it has even been severally reported that terrorist groups, especially in the northern part of the country have had the effrontery to overthrow the constitutionally installed local government council and install governments which are presided over by terrorists. According to Brechenmacher (2019), there were periods between 2015 and 2018, the boko haram group was in control of 17 local governments in Borno State, imposing and collecting taxes and other civic levies from residents. A report by the International Crisis Group (2018), claimed that between June 2015 and May 2018, the Boko Haram and Fulani herdsmen attack in the north eastern and northcentral parts of Nigeria had led to over 26, 500 deaths. Hence, Aderounmu (2021) informed that on many recorded occasions, the boko haram and Fulani herdsmen terror groups impose on farmers high taxes ranging from N70million to N10million, just to access farmlands rightfully belonging to the affected farmers.

Social Environment

In recent times, the Nigerian state has had one of the most perturbed, unhealthy, aggressive and volatile social environments around the globe. Consequently, there has been a flurry of civic agitations, demonstrations, petitions and media outpouring to register social misgivings over the state of affairs in the country. In 2023, bouts of violent protests that engulfed several cities in Nigeria over the unpopular naira redesign and cashless policy of former President Muhammadu Buhari, was a testament to the growing level of social discontent in the Nigerian society. Also, in 2024, the nationwide hunger protest was a public outcry and mass reactions over evident signs of bad governance that has characterised the current administration of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu since its inception in 2023. According to Lawal (2024), the 2024 Endbadgovernance protest in Nigeria which lasted for a period ten days represented a

vote of no confidence passed in the government at the centre by majority of hungry, despondent and frustrated Nigerians. Hence, according to a report by the World Food Programme (WFP), about 26.5 million Nigerians, between Q3 of 2023 and Q2 of 2024 were living in acute poverty and excruciating hunger. Particularly, the report by WFP disclosed that in the northeastern part of Nigeria, over 4.4 million people were food insecure. The report also indicated that 37% Nigerians were living below the national poverty threshold of \$2.15 daily. According to Ibrahim (2024), even though the government at the centre succeeded in using the instruments of coercion to suppress voices of dissent, yet, the Endbadgovernance protest of 2024 constitutes a serious threat to the legitimacy of the present government in power, as well as its sovereignty both internally and externally.

The Nation's Global Image

On account of the various aspects of poor governance in Nigeria, evidenced by the high degree of social discontent in various shades, the country's worth in the perception of the international community has continued to plummet over time. The various socio-economic indices used in evaluating a country's global image have continued to portray the Nigerian society in a bad light. In the aspect of Nigeria's electoral system, the reports by international observers on the outcome of the last three general elections in Nigeria indicate that the elections were marred with obvious and rampant malpractices and irregularities (Ekpei, 2023). In the area of public sector corruption, according to the report by Transparency International in 2024, Nigeria scored 26 points out of 100 on the Corruption Perception Index. This figure, based on the analysis by Transparency International indicates a very high rate of corruption in the public sector setting. And this, expectedly, does not speak well of Nigeria's image in global perception. In terms of human rights protection, the report by Amnesty International in 2024 portrayed Nigeria to be top among countries with very bad record of human right violations. The body cited instances with rampant extra-judicial killings and institutional prohibition of freedom of speech, as well as the indiscriminate harassment and intimidation of media personnel. The body made reference to a situation where on July 23, 2024, the House of Representatives introduced the Counter Subversion Bill- a bill which aimed at proposing very stringent penalties on Nigerians who failed to recite the newly approved national anthem. Also, the Amnesty International referred to an incident on 15 March 2024 where a journalist by name, Segun Olatunji was arbitrarily arrested by the Nigerian authorities for publishing a story on perceived acts of nepotism.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

State sovereignty, especially in a democratic crime must necessarily be built on the strict observance and practice of the ethics of good governance by the leadership of any politically independent state. The ability of the leadership of a state to successfully assert its authority on the people and conveniently enforce laws and regulations for the purpose of governance, must be sourced from the willful cooperation and endorsement of the people. Hence, any tendency by the leadership of a state to resort to options contrary to the above stated, flagrantly contravenes the ideals of state sovereignty in a democratic environment. Accordingly, popular sovereignty practiced in recent times by most countries which embrace and democracy suggests that sovereignty resides with the people and that the leadership of any sovereign state only hold it and use it judiciously in trust for the people.

In the course of this study, it was observed that the status of the Nigerian state as a supposedly sovereign entity has been severally challenged and grossly limited in recent times by a lot of administrative factors. Thus, these factors have over time, proven to be confrontational to sustaining the country's collective national security concerns. This study has critically observed that Nigeria's wobbling and deteriorating economic posture has continued to infringe on the country's social cohesion and stability. Again, the morally decadent style of politics in Nigeria which has often times, infiltrated and corrupted the country's governance system has also posed a very great question to Nigeria's claim to a sovereign status. In recent times, the persistence of the myriad of dilapidating and poor socio-economic and political indices has continued to give rise to uprisings, criminal indulgences and other degrees of national security confrontations.

To restore and sustain the ever-plunging Nigerian state's sovereignty status, it should be incumbent on the government to evolve salient strategies that would effectively grapple with the deteriorating situation. In addition to committing sufficient financial and administrative resources towards revitalising the economic base of the nation, the political leadership class should adopt a far-reaching distributive economic policy. This should be aimed at changing the culture of over-concentrating the nation's resources in the hands of a privileged few.

The political system should reflect a public governance structure which portrays a rebranded value system. The expected reforms in the public service normative values should be embraced by both political office holders, as well as public servants in the nation's bureaucratic system. The expected change would have the prospects of impacting positively on the nation's electoral system, mode of operations of security agencies, foreign policies and inter-governmental relations. Interestingly, it would achieve the ultimate goal of improving the plunging status of Nigeria's internal and external sovereignty status.

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